

Recent advances in dairy cattle production

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Introduction

Animal Husbandry and dairy development plays a prominent role in the rural economy in supplementing the income of rural household particularly, the landless and small and marginal farmers. It also provides subsidiary occupation in semi-urban areas and more so for people living in hilly, tribal and drought - prone areas where crop output may not sustain the family.

India is endowed with the largest livestock population in the world. It accounts for 57 per cent of the world's buffalo population and 15 per cent of the cattle population. The country has about 20.5 crore cattle and 8.4 crore buffaloes as compared to 15.5 crore cattle and 4.3 crore buffalo in 1951. A.H. output constitutes about 24 per cent of the country's agricultural output. According to estimates of national accounts, the gross value of output for livestock sector during 1998-99 was about Rs.1,23,077 crore as against the total value of output of Rs.5,07,297 crore for the agricultural sector. The production statistics of the country as well as of the state clearly indicate that the development of livestock has been undertaken, thereby augmentation of potential animals has been achieved.

In spite of many dairy development programmes organised by different agencies, the many farmers perceived a number of constraints with regard to dairy farming. In their views, these are hampering them in increasing the milk production. Non-remunerative price for the milk was perceived by 90 per cent of the respondents as a major constraint. This appeared to be genuine in view of the increased inputs cost and overall increase in the price for all food commodities.

Recent advances

The various cattle and buffalo development programmes, lay emphasis on genetic improvement of productivity, since augmentation of high milk producing animals is necessary to provide milk to the fast growing human population of our country. The Rajasthan state is advocating cross breeding of non-descript cattle with frozen semen of Jersey and Holstein exotic breeds. The exotic blood level will be kept between 50 to 62.5 per cent.

The state is famous for many recognized indigenous breed. Hence, in such tracts the policy of selection and upgradation of the indigenous breeds has been adopted. India's cattle are resistant to diseases especially to tropical animal diseases like tick-borne and protozoan infections. Various Central and Centrally sponsored schemes are being implemented for genetic improvement of cattle with a view to increasing the per capita availability of consumption of milk through increased milk production. Efforts are also made to protect and preserve the indigenous cattle in their native tract, which are facing threat of extinction. The elite animals are selected and registered on the basis of their performance for production of superior pedigree bulls, bull-mothers, frozen semen and frozen embryos for future breeding improvements. To achieve this, the advanced embryo transfer technology is also applied in breeding operations.

During 1999-2000 a total of 6,103 artificial insemination centres, 17 semen stations, 40 frozen semen banks, 66 LN2 delivery and distribution system and 10 training centres were established / strengthened in various states with central assistance. A Central sector scheme for production of proven bulls by progeny testing under field conditions has been in operation in Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Maharashtra, Orissa and Tamil Nadu. So far 45 number of bulls have been put under test-mating in the progeny testing centres. Under the National bull production programme 914 persons have been trained, 16 farms have been strengthened, five Goshalas were assisted, four bull stations for associated herd progeny testing programme were strengthened and two Embryo Transfer Training Centres were established. In 1999-2000, A total of 2,870 castrators were purchased by various States of this region for castration of the scrap bulls under mass castration programme. The following schemes are implemented through the State Governments with 100 per cent Central assistance : (a) Extension of frozen semen technology and progeny testing programme and (b) National bull production programme.

The seven central cattle breeding farms at Suratgarh

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(Rajasthan), Chiplima and Semiliguda (Orissa), Dhamrod (Gujarat), Hossarghatta (Karnataka), Alamadi (Tamil Nadu) and Andeshnagar (Uttar Pradesh) are engaged in scientific breeding programmes of cattle and buffaloes and production of high pedigreed bulls and frozen semen for cattle breeding projects. Cooperatives have played a significant role in stimulating dairy development in the country. The Operation Flood Programme, which was the world's largest integrated dairy development programme, has made considerable progress in achieving its outlined objectives. The programme has since completed its III phase in April 1996. By March 2000 about 84,289 dairy cooperative societies were organised in 170 milksheds involving over 10.61 million farmer members. As a result of various measures taken by the Government, milk production in the country has been 68.3 million tonnes at the end of Eighth plan (1996-97) as compared to 17 millions tonnes in 1950-51. India's milk output during 1998-99 was targeted to reach the level of 74.7 million tonnes. The National Bureau of Animal Genetic Resources has developed a fully operational information system on animal genetic resources of India. Breed calendar for 30 breeds of indigenous cattle was developed.

The cross breeding programme in the country has led to the development of new strains of cattles namely Karan Swiss, Karan Fries and Frieswal. The National Dairy Research Institute, Karnal has achieved distinction of possessing a Karan Fries Cow, "Kamadhenu" which produced 44.2kg milk per day at peak lactation.

In the field of animal nutrition technologies for improvement of cereal straws through alkali and urea treatment were developed. Biodegradable waste has been used as feed ingredient. Database was developed on Animal nutrition at NIANP, Bangalore. Embryo transfer technology was successfully used among buffalo, cattle, sheep and goat. In-vitro buffalo calves were successfully produced. 32 cells clones embryo in buffaloes was produced.

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ELISA based diagnostic kits for Infectious Bovine Rhinotracheitis (IBR) and Brucella, Elisa Kit for FMD, a liquid phase blocking Elisa test, Dot-Elisa for quick diagnosis of Hydropericardium syndrome etc, were developed. A high Security Animal Disease Laboratory (P4 Biosafety) has been established at Bhopal.

Extension facilities

The Indian Council of Agricultural Research has launched an innovative project called "Institute-Village-Linkage Programme" (IVLP) to ensure greater scientists farmers linkage. IVLP also ensures access to agricultural technology generated by the agricultural research system in the country to the entire farming community in a village or a cluster of villages representing around 1,000 farm facilities. So far 42 centres have been identified to cover 42,000 farm families. The council helps in the assessment and refinement of technologies in all disciplines of research conducted in the system and disseminates the latest agricultural technologies to farmers, extension functionaries and other agencies involved in the development of agriculture. The council has 261 Krishi Vigyan Kendras (KVKs) located in various states. These KVKs perform on-farm testing / research, vocational training farmers, farm women and rural youth, in-service training of grass-root level field functionaries and frontline demonstrations. These KVKs are district-level institutions run by the SAUs, ICAR Institutes and selected non-governmental organisations. Each year about two lakh farmers are trained at these KVKs in the areas of crop husbandry, horticulture, animal husbandry and dairying, fisheries and vocations leading to self-employment. There are eight Trainers' Training Centres (TTCs) which are subject specific training institutions in dryland agriculture, horticulture, farm machines, inland fisheries, marine fisheries, hill agriculture, dairying and home science. Training is imparted to KVK scientists and subject matter specialists by these TTCs to update their skill.

Conclusion

All livestock improvement programme should be viewed in terms of improving the productivity per unit animal through planned breeding, increasing feed and fodder resources and providing the optimal management levels. Any efforts made towards improving the livestock productivity in arid region will greatly benefit the socio-economic conditions of the rural people.